

The Influence of Competence and Training on Performance in the Education Department of Labuh batu District with Motivation as Intervening Variables

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ABSTRACT: Employee performance is a measure of how human resources in a company have played a role or not in the progress of the organization. The potential of well-performing human resources determines the success of the company. To achieve the best performance, of course, it is necessary to have directed management of human resources through various policies that can adjust the common interests of employees and the company. This study aims to determine whether competency and training affect employee performance through motivation as an intervening variable at the Labuhanbatu District Education Office. The study was conducted on 61 employees using a saturated sampling technique. The data collection technique used was primary data in the form of questionnaires and secondary data obtained through documentation studies. The data analysis technique used quantitative data which was processed using the SPSS version 25 program, namely the t test, Sobel test and path analysis. The results obtained in this study show 1) there is a significant influence between competence on motivation, 2) there is a significant effect between training variables on motivation, 3) there is a significant effect between competency variables on performance, 4) there is a significant effect between training variables on performance, 5) there is a significant influence between motivational variables on performance, 6) motivational variables cannot affect competency variables on performance, 7) motivational variables cannot influence training variables on performance.

KEYWORDS: Competence, Performance, Motivation, Training.

INTRODUCTION

The business world is now required to create high employee performance for the development of the company. Companies must be able to build and improve performance within their environment. The success of the company is influenced by several factors, one of the important factors is human resources, and human resources in a company play a very important role. The workforce has great potential to carry out the activities of the enterprise. The potential of every human resource in the company must be utilized as well as possible so that it is able to provide optimal output.

Employee performance is a measure of how human resources in a company have played a role or not in the progress of the organization. The potential of human resources who perform well determines the success of the company. To achieve the best performance, of course, it is necessary to manage directed human resources through various policies that can adjust the common interests between employees and the company. Kasmir (2016: 212) the importance of the role of human resources in achieving organizational performance with the capabilities of its human resources. Performance appraisal spurs on a formal and structured system used to measure, assess and influence work-related traits. Mangkunegara (2017: 10) performance evaluation must go through an assessment that is carried out systematically to find out the results of employee work and organizational performance.

Motivation is an important element and largely determines performance improvement. Creating great motivation in all employees is the responsibility of the organization, it is very important to take care of and maintain the work motivation of all employees, motivation at work can go up and down, have little dependence on the situation and condition of the organization Wibowo (2016). Competence is one of the determining factors in improving performance, so companies must pay attention to the problem of employee competence in the organization / company. Mathis and Jackson, (2012:46) put forward several competencies that individuals must possess. According to them, there are three competencies that a human resource practitioner must have, namely first knowledge of business and organization, then secondly knowledge of the influence and change of management and specific knowledge and expertise of human resources. In addition, companies must provide training programs for employees so that

employees can improve their knowledge, abilities and skills in carrying out work so that employee performance increases. The existence of this training will create high employee performance so that it can support the success of the company. With sufficient training programs and competencies possessed by employees, work will increasingly be understood and mastered in carrying out their profession. So that it can create benefits for the employees themselves as well as benefits for the company.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Performance is a comparison between the output achieved and the input given. In addition, performance is also the result of the efficiency of input management and the effectiveness of achieving goals, (Atmoseoprapto in Agustini, 2011: 88). According to Miner in Sutrisno (2011:170) performance is how a person who is expected and performs functions and behaves according to the duties that have been charged to him. It can be concluded that performance (prestasi kerja) is the result of work that can be achieved by employees in an organization, in accordance with the authority and responsibility given by the organization in an effort to achieve the vision, mission and objectives of the organization concerned legally, not violating the law and in accordance with morals or ethics.

Kasmir (2016: 208) to measure performance, several indicators can be used regarding performance criteria, namely: "quality, quantity, timeliness, cost-effectiveness, the need for supervision, and relationships between individuals. It is this indicator that will be the benchmark in measuring performance".

Motivation is an activity that results in a person completing their work with enthusiasm, willingness and full of responsibility. Motivation serves as a driver or encouragement to employees to be willing to work hard for the achievement of agency goals properly, for more details the following is a definition of motivation according to experts. Hasibuan (2009:95) motivation is the provision of driving force that creates a person's work excitement, so that they are willing to work together, work effectively, and integrate with all their efforts to achieve satisfaction.

McClelland in Jimmy (2014: 499) defines competence as a fundamental characteristic that a person has that has a direct influence on, or can predict, excellent performance. Meanwhile, Palan (2007:6), says that competence consists of several different types of characteristics, which encourage behavior. The foundation of this characteristic is evident in the way a person behaves at work. Competence is about what kind of person and what they can do, not what they might do. Competence is found in people who are classified as superior or effective performers. Competence is a combination of skills, knowledge, creativity and a positive attitude towards a particular work that is embodied in performance. Competence is the character of a worker who is able to produce good performance compared to others (Darsono and Siswandoko, 2011:123).

METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted at the Education Office of Labuhan Batu Regency which is located at Jalan Menara, No. 7, Rantauprapat, Labuhan Batu Regency, North Sumatra. Meanwhile, the research time was carried out from October 2022 to January 2023.

A hypothesis is a temporary answer to a research problem, until it is proven through the collected data. The hypotheses of the study are:

- H1: Competence has a significant effect on motivation.
- H2: Training has a significant effect on motivation.
- H3: Competence has a significant effect on performance
- H4: Training has a significant effect on performance
- H5: Motivation has a significant effect on performance
- H6: Competence has a significant effect on performance through motivation
- H7: Training has a significant effect on performance through motivation

Figure: Conceptual Framework

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. T TEST

Sub Model II t Test Results

Coefficients^a

Type	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	4,602	3,660		1,258	,214
Competence	,306	,091	,273	3,350	,001
Training	,289	,074	,435	3,898	,000
Motivation	,285	,115	,289	2,474	,016

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Source : Primary Data Processed, 2022

On the table, a statistical test t is obtained, as follows:

1)Motivation Variable (Z), with a probability level of 0.016. Thus it can be concluded $P = 0.016 < \alpha = 0.05$, then accept the hypothesis that states the motivational variable has a significant effect on performance.

2)Competency Variable (X1), with a probability level of 0.001 Thus it can be inferred $P = 0.001 < \alpha = 0.05$, then accept the hypothesis that states the competency variable has a significant effect on performance.

3)Training Variable (X2), with a probability level of 0.000. Thus it can be concluded $P = 0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$, hence the hypothesis that states the training variable has a significant effect on performance.

Thus can be compiled the path analysis equation as follows :

$$Y = 0.273 X1 + 0.435 X2 + 0.289 Z$$

The analysis equation model means:

1)Competency Variable (X1) = 0.273. A competency variable that is positively marked means that it has a unidirectional influence, which means that each addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the competency variable will add a performance variable value of 0.273 per one unit score.

2)Training variable (X2) = 0.435. A training variable that is positively marked means that it has a unidirectional influence, which means that each addition or increase in the value of one unit of training variable score will add a performance variable value of 0.435 per one unit score.

3)Motivation Variable (Z) = 0.289. A motivational variable marked positive means that it has a unidirectional influence, which means that each addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the motivation variable will add a performance variable value of 0.289 per one unit score.

B. SOBEL TEST

The Sobel test is carried out by testing the strength of the indirect influence X to Y through Z, as follows:

$$Z = \frac{ab}{\sqrt{(b^2SE_a^2 + a^2SE_b^2)}}$$

Where:

a = regression coefficient of the independent variable on the mediating variable

b = regression coefficient of the mediating variable on the dependent variable

SEa = standard error of estimation from the influence of the independent variable on the mediating variable

SEb = standard error of estimation of the effect of the mediating variable on the dependent variable

The following are the results of the Sobel test with the variable supervision of performance through OCB.

$$t = \frac{0.023 \times 0.143}{\sqrt{(0.143^2 \times 0.204^2) + (0.023^2 \times 0.072^2)}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.023 \times 0.143}{\sqrt{0.0008510056 + 0.000027423}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.003289}{0.0008537479}$$

$$t = 3.852$$

From the results of the calculation of the sobel test above, it obtained a t value of 3,852, so that a calculated t value of 3,852 > t table 0,870, it can be concluded that the OCB variable is able to mediate the relationship between the influence of supervision on performance.

The following are the results of the Sobel test with the variable Job satisfaction on performance through OCB.

$$t = \frac{0.098 \times 0.143}{\sqrt{(0.143^2 \times 0.163^2) + (0.098^2 \times 0.057^2)}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.098 \times 0.143}{\sqrt{0.0005433095 + 0.0000312034}}$$

$$t = \frac{0.014014}{0.0005745129}$$

$$t = 24.392$$

From the results of the calculation of the sobel test above, it obtains a t value of 24,392, so that a calculated t value of 24,392 > t table is 2,246. It can be concluded that the OCB variable is able to mediate the relationship between the effect of job satisfaction on performance.

C. PATH ANALYSIS

Figure Model II Sub Path Diagram

of the analysis show that the direct influence given by Competence (X1) on Performance (Y) is 0.273. Meanwhile, the indirect influence of Competence (X1) on Performance (Y) through Motivation (Z), which is $0.208 \times 0.435 = 0.090$. Then the effect of the total given by the Competency variable (X1) on Performance (Y) is a direct influence coupled with an indirect influence, which is $0.273 + 0.090 = 0.36$. Based on the results of the above calculations, it can be known that the value of direct influence is 0.273 and an indirect influence of 0.090, which means that the value of direct influence is greater than that of indirect influence. These results show that indirectly the variable Competence (X1) through Motivation (Z) has no significant impact on Performance (Y). The results of the analysis showed that the direct influence provided by Training (X2) on Performance (Y) was 0.435. While the indirect influence of Training (X2) on Performance (Y) through Motivation (Z), which is $0.686 \times 0.289 = 0.198$. Then the total effect that the Training variable (X2) gives to Performance (Y) is a direct influence coupled with an indirect influence, which is $0.435 + 0.198 = 0.63$. Based on the results of the above calculations it can be known that the value of direct influence is 0.435 and indirect influence by 0.198, which means that the value of direct influence is greater than the value of indirect influence. These results show that indirectly the training variable (X2) through Motivation (Z) has no significant effect on Performance (Y).

Total Influence Values

No.	Influence	Direct Influence	Indirect Influence	Total Influence
1	X1 → Y	0.273	$0.208 \times 0.435 = 0.090$	0.36
2	X2 → Y	0.435	$0.686 \times 0.289 = 0.198$	0.63

DISCUSSION

A. The effect of Competence on Motivation

The competency variable has a positive and significant effect on motivation at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The competency variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.208 has a unidirectional effect, which means that any addition or increase in the value of a unit of competency variable score will increase the motivation value of labuhanbatu education office employees by 0.208 per unit score.

Based on the results of the first hypothesis testing, it is known that competence has a significant influence on the motivation of the Labuhanbatu Education Office. This is supported by research conducted by Arif Triyanto and Sudarwati (2014), revealing that competence has an influence on motivation.

B. The effect of Training on Motivation

The training variable has a positive and significant effect on motivation at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The training variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.686 has a unidirectional effect, which means that every addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the training variable akan adds to the motivational value of the employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office by 0.686 per unit score.

Based on the results of the second hypothesis test, it is known that training has a significant influence on the motivation of employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office. This is supported by research conducted by Yuyun Yuniar Darmawan, Wayan Gede Supartha and Agoes Ganesha Rahyuda (2017), revealing that training has a significant influence on motivation.

C. The effect of Motivation on Performance

The motivation variable has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The motivation variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.289 has a unidirectional influence which means that every addition or increase in the value of one unit score of the motivation variable will increase the performance value of labuhanbatu education office employees by 0.289 per unit score.

Based on the results of the fifth hypothesis test, it is known that motivation has a significant influence on the performance of employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office. This is in accordance with research conducted by Ignatius Ario Sumbogo and Ngadino Surip Diposumarto (2017), who found that motivation can improve employee performance.

D. The effect of Competence on Performance

The competency variable has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The competency variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.273 has a unidirectional effect, which means that any increase in the value of one unit of competency variable score will increase the performance value of labuhanbatu education office employees by 0.273 per unit score.

Based on the results of the third hypothesis test, it is known that competence has a significant influence on the performance of employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The findings of this study are supported by research conducted by Nisa' Ulul Mafra (2017), which states that competence has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

E. The effect of Training on Performance

The training variable has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The training variable has a regression coefficient value of 0.435 has a unidirectional effect, which means that any increase in the value of one unit of training variable score will increase the performance value of the Labuhanbatu Education Office by 0.435 per one unit score.

Based on the results of the fourth hypothesis testing, it is known that training has a significant influence on the performance of employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The results of this study are in accordance with research conducted by Elizar and Hasrudy Tanjung (2018) also states that training has a positive and significant effect on performance.

F. The effect of Competence on Performance through Motivation

Based on the results of the sobel test calculation, it is known that the t value is 43,222, so that the calculated t value of 43,222 > t table 3,887 is obtained, so it can be concluded that the motivation variable is able to mediate the relationship and influence of competence on performance. And based on the track analysis, it is known that the magnitude of the influence of competence (X1) on the performance (Y) of employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office is 36%, which consists of a direct influence of 27.3% and an indirect influence of competence (X1) on performance (Y) through motivation (Z) of 9%. The results of this calculation show that the direct influence of competence (X1) on performance (Y) is greater than its indirect influence. Thus it can be said that competence is effective in improving performance, in other words it can be affirmed that competence (X1) has an influence if there is an increase in employee performance in carrying out tasks.

Based on the results of the sixth hypothesis test, it is known that competence through motivation has an influence on the performance of employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The results showed that motivation has no role in mediating competence in performance.

G. The effect of Training on Performance through Motivation

Based on the results of the sobel test calculation, it is known that the t value is 30,433, so that the calculated t value of 30,433 > t table 3,887 is obtained, it can be concluded that the motivation variable is able to mediate the relationship of the influence of training on performance. And based on the track analysis, it is known that the magnitude of the influence of training (X2) on the performance (Y) of employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office is 63%, which consists of a direct influence of 43.5% and an indirect influence of training (X2) on performance (Y) through motivation (Z) of 19.8%. The results of this calculation show that the direct influence of training (X2) on performance (Y) is more than the indirect influence. Thus it can be said that the influence of training (X2) will be smaller in improving performance (Y) if it is carried out through motivation (Z).

Based on the results of the seventh hypothesis test, it is known that motivational melalui training has an influence on the performance of employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office. The results showed that motivation has no role in mediating the influence of training on performance.

CONCLUSIONS

Competent is has a positive and significant effect on motivation at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. This means that this condition proves that employee competence can increase motivation at work. The effect of competence on the performance of employees of the Labu Hanbatu Education Office will be smaller if it is carried out through motivation. The direct influence of competence on

employee performance is greater than the indirect influence of competence on performance. It can be concluded that motivation is unable to mediate the influence of competence on performance.

Training has a positive and significant effect on performance at the Labuhanbatu Education Office. This means that this condition proves that the existence of training can improve employee performance. The effect of training on the performance of employees of the Labuhanbatu Education Office will be smaller if it is carried out through motivation. The direct influence of training on performance is greater than the indirect influence of training on performance. It can be concluded that motivation is not able to mediate the influence of training on performance.

REFERENCES

1. Agustini, Fauzia. 2011. *Advanced Human Resource Management* (First Edition). Medan: Madenatera Publishers.
2. Ghozali, Imam. 2018. *Multi variate analysis applications with IBM SPSS 25 programs*. Jakarta : Diponegoro University Publisher.
3. Ghozali, Imam. 2016. *Multivariate Analysis Applications With IBM SPSS 23 Programs* (8th Edition). Prints to VIII. Semarang : Diponegoro University IT Research Agency.
4. Hasibuan, Malayu S. 2008. *Organization and Motivation : Basis for Increasing Productivity*. Bumi Aksara: Jakarta.
5. Hasibuan, S.P Malayu (2009). *Organization and Basic Motivation for Productivity Improvement*. 7th printing. Jakarta: PT Bumi Aksara.
6. Hasrudy, Elizar. 2018. The Effect of Training, Competence and Work Environment on Employee Performance. Scientific Journal of Masters. volume 1 , Number 1.
7. Hussein Umar. 2013. *Research Methods for Thesis and Thesis*, Rajawali, Jakarta.
8. Kuncoro, Mudrajad. 2013. *Research Methods For Business and Economics*. 3rd edition. Jakarta: Erlangga.
9. Kuncoro, Mudrajad. 2011. *Research Methods for Business & Economics*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
10. Mangkunegara, Anwar Prabu. 2013. *Management of Corporate Human Resources* (12th Printing). Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
11. Mangkunegara, Anwar Prabu (2012). *Management of Corporate Human Resources*. 12th printing. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
12. Mangkunegara, Anwar Prabu (2017). *Management of Corporate Human Resources*. 12th printing. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
13. Newstrom, John W. & Keith Davis. 2004. *Behavior in organizations* 7th Edition . Jakarta: Erlangga.
14. Sugiyono. 2012. *Business Research Methods*. London: Alfabeta.
15. Sutrisno, Edy. 2011. *Organizational Culture* (1st Edition). Jakarta : Kencana Publisher (Prenada Media Group).
16. Sugiyono. (2018). *Quantitative, Quality and R & D. Research Methods* Bandung: Alfabeta.
17. Sumbogo, Diposumarto. 2017. The Effect of Competence and Training on Reporter Performance with Motivation as an Intervening variable. UNIAT Journal of Economists.
18. Sudarwati, Arif. 2014. The Effect Of Competence And Appreciation On The Work Motivation Of Pt Kai Employees At Sragen Station.
19. Ulul, Nisa. 2017. The Effect of Competence and Communication on the Performance of PT. Bukit Asam (Persero), Tbk Kertapati Palembang Pier Unit. Volume 2, Number 1.
20. Yuniar, Wayan and Rahyuda. 2017. The Effect Of Training On Work Motivation And Performance In Prama Sanur Beach-Bali.
21. Yukl, Gary. 2009. *Leadership In Organizations*. Language transfer: Budi Supriyanto. Jakarta: Index.

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